

Terpenoids. Part IX. Synthesis of ($\pm$)-Isopulegone

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The synthesis of ($\pm$)-isopulegone has been accomplished through an application of the Wittig reaction with methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide on 2-acetyl-5-methyl-(1-keto-1-dioxolane)cyclohexane and deketalisation of the resulting product under mild conditions.

Isopulegone, a monocyclic monoterpene ketone, occurs along with pulegone in essential oils¹. The structure (I) has been assigned to it on the basis of chemical evidence, spectral data¹, and its relationship to isopulegol and pulegone¹.

The present studies constitute a clean synthesis of ($\pm$)-isopulegone.

2-Acetyl-5-methyl-(1-keto-1-dioxolane)cyclohexane² (II), prepared in our laboratory, was submitted to Wittig's reaction³ with methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide in presence of methyl sulphanyl carbanion and under nitrogen atmosphere to furnish 2-isopropenyl-5-methyl-(1-keto-1-dioxolane)cyclohexane (III) in 58.9% yield. The ketal (III) after purification through alumina column showed characteristic IR peaks⁴ at 892, 1650 ($\frac{R_I}{R_{II}} > C = CH_2$), 1065 (ketal), 1389, and 1460 cm^{-1} (C-Me)

The compound (III) on deketalisation⁵ with PTS in acetone at the room temperature, followed by purification through chromatography, furnished isopulegone (2-isopropenyl-5-methylcyclohexanone) (I) in 54% yield.

The synthetic ketone was characterised through its 2,4-DNP, m p. 136°, and IR absorption spectrum which showed peaks⁴ at 892 and 1650 ($\frac{R_I}{R_{II}} > C = CH_2$), 1715 (C = O), 1378, and 1460 cm^{-1} (C-Me).

1. Pinder, "The Chemistry of the Terpenes", Chapman & Hall Ltd., London, 1960, pp. 69, 60.
2. Vig *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1964, **41**, 420.
3. Greenwald *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 1128.
4. Cross, "Introduction to Practical I. R. Spectroscopy", Butterworth's Scientific Publications, London, 1960, pp. 58-63.
5. Johnson *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 862.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Acetyl-5-methyl (1-keto-1-dioxolane)cyclohexane (II) was prepared according to the procedure described in the literature². IR absorption spectrum of this compound showed peaks⁴ at 1725 (C=O), 1060 (ketal), 1375, and 1465 cm^{-1} (C-Me).

2-Isopropenyl 5-methyl (1-keto-1-dioxolane)cyclohexane (III).—A solution of methyl sulphanyl carbanion was prepared under nitrogen atmosphere from sodium hydride (0.69 g.) and dimethyl sulphoxide (7 ml). The solution was cooled in an ice-cold bath and stirred during addition of methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (5.76 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (14.0 ml) when the reddish colour of the methylenephosphorane was produced. After stirring at the room temperature for 15 min. the ketal-ketone (II, 1.4 g.) in THF (12 ml) was added and stirring continued for 2 hr. at 60°. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured on cold water. The organic layer was taken up in light petroleum and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residue was chromatographed through neutral alumina when the first fraction on vacuum distillation afforded (III) in 0.8 g. (58.92%) yield; b.p. 100°/3-4 mm; $n_D^{20.5}$ 1.4740. (Found: C, 73.47; H, 10.20. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 73.00; H, 10.19%).

2-Isopropenyl-5-methylcyclohexanone(I).—To the above compound (III, 0.5 g.) were added acetone (12 ml), *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.15 g.), and water (1.5 ml) and the reaction mixture was stirred at the room temperature for 1 hr. After removing the excess of PTS with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution, the product was extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residue was purified as in (III) and the required fractions on distillation under reduced pressure furnished (I) in 0.2 g. (54%) yield, b.p. 70°/2-3 mm, $n_D^{20.5}$ 1.4700. (Found: C, 78.67; H, 10.47. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ requires C, 78.60; H, 10.40%).

The 2,4-DNP, prepared by the sulphuric acid method in cold, was recrystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals, m.p. 136° (lit⁵ records m.p. 136--37°). (Found: N, 16.70. Calc. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$: N, 16.80%).

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Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalyses by Mr. B. N. Anand, Microanalyst, Panjab University Chemistry Department, Chandigarh. I.R. spectra were recorded in Beckman I.R.-5 with sodium chloride optics using a thin liquid film.

6. Lloyd *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 2306.